

Church of St. Pelagia, Ano Viannos, Heraklion, Crete

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Entry tags: Greece, Religious Group, Byzantine, Church, Crete, Byzantine, Religious Place, Medieval Christianity, Orthodoxy, Monument

Located in the village of Ano Viannos, south of the capital city of Heraklion, the Church of St. Pelagia is a single nave chapel with a pointed barrel vault interior and saddle roof exterior. The church is whitewashed except for the stone frame decorating the entrance on the southern wall. A framed pointed-arch niche, also whitewashed, rises above the lintel with traces of painting still visible where the stone meets the whitewash. The door frame and niche are undecorated. A transverse arch divides the interior of the church into two bays while a short modern banister divides the sanctuary from the nave. In the sanctuary, although badly damaged by smoke and moisture, the half dome of the apse includes the image of the Virgin Platytera. She is flanked by two angels and extends her hands on either side of the roundel holding an image of the Christ child. The triumphal arch includes the scene of the Hospitality of Abraham in the upper register, the Annunciation on either side and, on the lower register, the images of the deacon St. Stephen on the left and an unidentifiable saint on the right. Behind the altar, four co-officiating bishops flank the Melismos. The Ascension is painted in the vault above the sanctuary. Below the Ascension, on the northern wall, is the image of the Pentecost, while opposite, on the southern wall, is the Presentation of the Virgin in the Temple. The lower register of the northern wall of the sanctuary includes the image of the Sacrifice of Abraham (just above the prothesis niche and east of a small window) while the south wall bears the image of an unidentifiable bishop saint next to St. Constantine. The barrel vault of the nave, to the east of the transverse arch, has scenes from the Christological cycle including the Anastasis, the Raising of Lazarus, Christ appearing to the two Marys and the Incredulity of Thomas. Additional scenes from the life of Christ as well as the life of St. Pelagia of Jerusalem decorate the barrel vault to the west of the transverse arch. These include, from the life of Christ, images of the Nativity, the Massacre of the Innocents and the Last Supper. From the life of St. Pelagia we have three scenes: St. Pelagia with two figures, St. Pelagia giving her belongings to the poor, and the deacon James visiting Pelagia in her cell. The transverse arch is decorated with the Ten saints of Crete. The gallery of saints along the northern wall (to the west of the modern iconostasis) includes the images of St. Mamas, St. Anthony and, unusually, St. Bartholomew holding his skin over his left shoulder. Above the image of St. Bartholomew, who stands directly below the transverse arch, is the image of a cross-legged male figure playing a lute (possibly connected to the life of St. Pelagia). Next to St. Bartholomew are three military saints on horseback. Likewise, the saints on the southern wall include (to the east of the entrance) an unidentifiable female saint, a bishop saint. To the right of the entrance is a large image of St. Christopher carrying the Christ child. The southern wall is decorated with the Crucifixion above and Hell below. Hell includes several frames of individual sinners and compartments of Communal Punishments spread across two registers. The individual sinners are well preserved and are presented in ochre against a white background. Each of the figures has a snake wrapped around them but the inscriptions are, for the most part lost. Of the ones that can be positively identified are: the (livestock) thief, the man who cheats the scales, the cheating tailor, the male and female fornicator, possibly the notary who falsified documents, the usurer, the fortune teller, the female slanderer, the witch and the woman who rejects babies. The dedicatory inscription for the church is located on the upper part of the portal. It notes that the church was built and decorated by Nikole(tos) Maris, his wife Sophia and their children, Kostas Maris, his wife and children, and their mother Eudokia on 1 October 6869 (1360). The church of St. Pelagia is known for its incorporation of several western iconographic elements into the decoration of the church. This includes the image of St. Bartholomew, flayed and carrying his skin (according to the western tradition

of his martyrdom), the image of St. Christopher holding the Christ child on his shoulder and the inclusion of the Centurion on horseback and Mary fainting in the scene of the Crucifixion.

Date Range: 1360 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Ano Viannos, Heraklion, Crete

Region tags: Greece, Crete

The village of Ano Viannos is located at an altitude of 500m on the southern slopes of the Dikti mountain range in the region of Heraklion on the island of Crete.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: Located inside the village of Ano Viannos.

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Other [specify]: It is a single nave chapel.

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: Both.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

–Yes [specify]: Dedicated to St. Pelagia.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Spatharakis, Ioannis. *Dated Byzantine Wall Paintings of Crete*. Leiden: Alexandros Press, 2001. See 111-14, no. 39.

– Source 2: Lymberopoulou, Angeliki, ed. *Hell in the Byzantine World: A History of Art and Religion in Venetian Crete and the Eastern Mediterranean*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020. See cat.

no. 76.

– Source 3: Theocharopoulou, R. “Ο τοιχογραφικός του Ναού της Αγίας Πελαγίας Βιάννου.” In Πεπραγμένα του Ζ' Διεθνούς Κρητολογικού Συνεδρίου, Β1:285–305. Rethymnon, 1995.

Notes: Borboudakis, Manolis, Klaus Gallas, and Klaus Wessel. Byzantinisches Kreta. Munich: Hirmer Verlag München, 1983. See p. 450-3. Gerola, Giuseppe, and K. Lassithiotakis. Τοπογραφικός κατάλογος των τοιχογραφημένων εκκλησιών της Κρήτης. Edited by K. Lassithiotakis. Heraklion: Εταιρίας Κρητικών Ιστορικών Μελετών, 1961. See no. 734. Gerola, Giuseppe. Monumenti Veneti nell'isola di Creta. 4 vols. Venice: R. Instituto Veneto di Scienze, Lettere ed Arti, 1932. See Vol. II, 346, no. 47

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Other [specify]: According to the dedicatory inscription the church was built and decorated by Nikole(tos) Maris, his wife Sophia and their children, Kostas Maris, his wife and children, and their mother Eudokia on 1 October 6869 (1360).

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Spatharakis, Ioannis. Dated Byzantine Wall Paintings of Crete. Leiden: Alexandros Press, 2001. See 111-14, no. 39.

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Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: Located inside the village of Ano Viannos.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

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↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: It is a single nave chapel.

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– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: Both.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Dedicated to St. Pelagia.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

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– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
– Yes

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife
– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
– Yes

↳ Humans
– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Plaster, brick and stone.

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

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↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
– Yes

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

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↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
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↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife
– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
– Yes

↳ Humans
– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is divination present:

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– I don't know

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– I don't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– I don't know

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– I don't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service.

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Church of St. Pelagia, Ano Viannos, Heraklion, Crete, Spatharakis, Ioannis. Dated Byzantine Wall Paintings of Crete. Leiden: Alexandros Press, 2001. p.111-14, no. 39

Reference: Church of St. Pelagia, Ano Viannos, Heraklion, Crete, Gerola, Giuseppe. Monumenti Veneti Nell'isola Di Creta. Venice: R. Instituto Veneto di Scienze, Lettere ed Arti, 1932. p.Vol. II, 346, no. 47

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